

Equation to Account Quantitatively for the Variation of Apparent Molal Volume of Strong Electrolytes in Solution According to Cube Root of Concentration

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From a consideration of the chemical potential of the ions of a strong electrolyte dissolved in water it has been found that κ (kappa) of the Debye-Hückel theory requires modification. Further theoretical considerations have led to the conclusion that the modified kappa, denoted by κ_m , should vary with dilution according to cube-root of concentration. Equations deduced by using this κ_m show that partial molal volume and apparent molal volume of a strong electrolyte in solution should vary with dilution according to cube root of concentration. The equation for the apparent molal volume has been subjected to test using the data available in the literature on NaCl, KCl, NaBr, NH_4NO_3 , Na_2SO_4 and SrCl₂ and has been found satisfactory.

REDLICH and Rosenfeld¹ have shown that variation of the partial molal volume \bar{V}_2 with pressure P of a strong electrolyte in solution is related to change in its free energy ($\bar{F}_2 - \bar{F}_2^0$) and the mean activity coefficient, f, by equation (1).

$$\bar{V}_2 - \bar{V}_2^0 = \frac{\partial(\bar{F}_2 - \bar{F}_2^0)}{\partial P} = \nu RT \frac{\partial \ln f}{\partial P} \quad \dots (1)$$

In equation (1) νRT has got its usual significance.

Since κ (kappa) and hence $\ln f$ in the Debye-Hückel theory varies as \sqrt{C} , it follows from equation (1) that

$$\bar{V}_2 = \bar{V}_2^0 + S_{(v)} \sqrt{C} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $S_{(v)}$ is a constant at constant temperature and pressure.

Masson² has found that the apparent molal volume ϕ_v of a strong electrolyte in solution varies with dilution according to equation (3).

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S \sqrt{C} \quad \dots (3)$$

where S remains constant at a given temperature and pressure.

According to LaMer and Gronwall³, Scott⁴, Geffeken⁵ and others⁶ $\bar{V}_2^0 = \phi_v^0$ and variation of ϕ_v according to \sqrt{C} has been attributed to interionic attraction as postulated in the Debye-Hückel theory. Geffeken⁵ and Gucker⁶ have shown that so long as \bar{V}_2 and ϕ_v vary according to \sqrt{C} only, the relation $(3/2)S = S_{(v)}$ holds good. Hence \bar{V}_2 may be calculated by using the equation (2a).

$$\bar{V}_2 = \phi_v^0 + 3/2 S \sqrt{C} \quad \dots (2a)$$

It may be mentioned that for KCl, NaBr and NaCl equation (3a) has been found by Geffeken and

Price⁷ to hold good,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + 1.9 \sqrt{C} + AC \quad \dots (3a)$$

where A is a constant.

In previous publications⁸⁻¹⁰ a modified expression for κ of the Debye-Hückel theory was deduced by applying Boltzmann's distribution formula taking the mean activity coefficient of the ions into consideration. The expression for the modified kappa, denoted by κ_m , may be written as

$$\kappa_m = (4\pi e^2 / DkT)^{1/2} (2nf_0/f)^{1/2}$$

In the aforesaid expression all the terms have their usual significance. Another relatively more simple way of deducing the same expression for κ_m is discussed below.

In a 1 : 1 strong electrolyte solution the chemical potential μ of the ions within the ion-atmosphere of the central ion (say positively charged) at a distance r from it may be written as

$$\mu_1 = \mu_0 + RT \ln(n_+)(n_-)f^2 \quad \dots (a)$$

where n_+ and n_- represent the numbers of positive and negative ions per unit volume and f their mean activity coefficient.

In the bulk of the solution at a point where the potential due to the central ion is zero the chemical potential μ_2 of the ions may be written as

$$\mu_2 = \mu_0 + RT \ln(nf_0)^2 \quad \dots (b)$$

where n represents the number of positive or negative ions per unit volume (since $n_+ = n_-$) and f_0 their mean activity coefficient. *As the system is in

* It follows from equation (c) that $(n_+)(n_-)f^2 = (nf_0)^2$ which is Donnan's equation for membrane equilibrium.

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equilibrium, so

$$\mu_1 = \mu_2 \text{ or } RT \ln (n_+)(n_-)f^2 = RT \ln (nf_0)^2 \dots (c)$$

Hence we may write

$$\left[\frac{kT}{e} \right] \ln [(n_+)f/nf_0] = \left[\frac{kT}{e} \right] \ln [nf_0/(n_-)f] = -\psi \dots (d)$$

where ψ is the potential difference between the two points under consideration and k , T and e have their usual significance.

It follows⁺ from equation (d) that,

$$n_- = [nf_0/f] \exp(c\psi/kT) \text{ and } n_+ = (nf_0/f) \exp(-c\psi/kT) \dots (e)$$

Now applying Poisson's equation and assuming linear approximation we get,

$$V^2\psi = -4\pi\rho/D = \left[\frac{4\pi e^2}{DkT} 2n(f_0/f) \right] \psi = \kappa_m^2 \psi \dots (f)$$

$$\text{Hence, } \kappa_m = \left[\frac{4\pi e^2}{DkT} 2n_f f_0/f \right]^{1/2} \dots (g)$$

Starting from equation (g) and adopting the same procedure as was followed in the previous papers⁸⁻¹⁰ it can be shown that $\kappa_m = [2e^2/DkTa]^{1/2} \times (2n)^{1/2}$ where a is the effective ionic diameter. Hence κ_m varies as $C^{1/2}$ so long as a remains constant.

Equations (2) and (3) can, therefore, be modified and the validity of the modified equations can be tested. As considerable amount of accurate data on apparent molal volume of strong electrolytes are available in the literature so modification of equation (3) is taken up first. It may be written as follows:

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + (S/\beta)\beta \sqrt{C} = \phi_v^0 + (S/\beta)\kappa \dots (3b)$$

where $\beta \sqrt{C}$ is equal to κ . For a 1 : 1 electrolyte at 25° $\beta = 0.3291 \times 10^8$ and $\kappa_m = \beta(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/2}$.

Substituting κ_m in place of κ in equation (3b) it may be written as:

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/2} \dots (3c)$$

$$= \phi_v^0 + KC^{1/2}, \text{ where } K \text{ is a constant} \dots (3d)$$

Adopting the same line of argument as stated above the modified form of equation (2) may be written as:

$$\bar{V}_2 = \phi_v^0 + S_{(v)}(1.22/\sqrt{a})C^{1/2} \dots (2b)$$

$$= \phi_v^0 + K_{(v)}C^{1/2}, \text{ where } K_{(v)} = S_{(v)}(1.22/\sqrt{a}) \dots (2c)$$

It may be pointed out that $S_{(v)}$ and S of equations (2b) and (3c) may differ from the corresponding constants of equations (2) and (3) as they are now functions of a , the effective ionic diameter, also in addition to those mentioned in standard books¹¹.

⁺It may be noted that in the limit when $f=f_0=1$, equation (e) becomes identical with the Boltzmann's distribution formula.

It may also be mentioned that if \bar{V}_2 and ϕ_v vary according to equations (2c) and (3c) then $K_{(v)}$ of equation (2c) should be equal to (4/3) K of equation (3d). This can be shown by adopting the same procedure as that of Geffeken⁵. Therefore, \bar{V}_2 may also be calculated by using equation (4).

$$\bar{V}_2 = \phi_v^0 + 4/3 KC^{1/2} \dots (4)$$

It may be mentioned in this connection that ϕ_v^0 of equation (4) will be different from ϕ_v^0 of equation (3).

In the following section equation (3d) has been subjected to test using the data available in the literature on a few strong electrolytes. It may be mentioned that at high concentrations a term involving C has to be added to equation (3d) for NaCl, NaBr and KCl and it may be written as

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + KC^{1/2} + K_1C \dots (3e)$$

where K_1 is a constant.

Source and processing of data :

In Tables 1 and 2 are recorded the values of ϕ_v at 25° at different concentrations, C , of the electrolytes mentioned. They are collected from the papers of the authors referred to. Under the head miscella-

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF ϕ_v OF 1 : 1 ELECTROLYTES WITH DILUTION AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values of ϕ_v		C	Values of ϕ_v	
		Observed	Calculated		Observed	Calculated
NaCl Equation (3e) $\phi_v^0 = 16.8$ $K = 1.88$ $K_1 = 0.96$	0.0186	16.86	16.80	0.7402	18.24	18.26
	0.0612	17.08	17.04	0.9739	18.52	18.51
	0.0793	17.10	17.11	1.027	18.59	18.57
	0.1032	17.22	17.20	1.613	19.10	19.08
	0.1806	17.41	17.42	1.836	19.28	19.26
	0.3656	17.76	17.78	1.913	19.31	19.30
0.3818	17.77	17.80	2.565	19.83	19.82	
KCl Equation (3e) $\phi_v^0 = 26.62$ $K = 1.72$ $K_1 = 0.5$	0.0099	26.99	26.99	1.101	28.96	28.95
	0.0203	27.08	27.09	1.313	29.18	29.17
	0.0603	27.29	27.32	1.495	29.35	29.34
	0.0737	27.35	27.37	1.787	29.61	29.60
	0.3973	28.06	28.08	2.055	29.85	29.84
	0.6538	28.43	28.44	2.335	30.06	30.06
0.8871	28.72	28.72	2.577	30.24	30.27	
NaBr Equation (3e) $\phi_v^0 = 23.11$ $K = 1.95$ $K_1 = 0.215$	0.0472	23.85	23.85	1.181	25.41	25.43
	0.0526	23.89	23.87	1.254	25.45	25.47
	0.0976	24.06	24.05	1.754	25.83	25.84
	0.1491	24.18	24.18	2.051	26.01	26.03
	0.1585	24.19	24.20	2.439	26.25	26.25
	0.3457	24.53	24.55	3.604	26.56	26.55
0.6549	24.91	24.94	3.907	27.002	27.02	
NH ₄ NO ₃ Equation (3d) $\phi_v^0 = 46.98$ $K = 1.54$	0.0905	47.71	47.68	0.3986	48.12	48.11
	0.1918	47.86	47.88	0.5138	48.22	48.21
	0.2104	47.90	47.90	0.9052	48.47	48.47
	0.2556	47.97	47.96	1.325	48.68	48.67
	0.3114	48.03	48.02	1.627	48.80	48.79
	1.627	48.80	48.79	3.442	49.47	49.48
NH ₄ NO ₃ Equation (3d) $\phi_v^0 = 46.38$ $K = 2.05$	2.099	49.01	49.00	3.869	49.60	49.60
	2.373	49.11	49.12	4.114	49.67	49.67
	2.809	49.26	49.27	4.448	49.76	49.75

neous are mentioned the electrolytes, the equation used and the values of the constants in them.

The data on NaCl concentration 0.0186 to 0.7402 *M* (ref. 12) and 0.973 to 2.565 *M* (ref. 5), on KCl concentration 0.0099 to 0.0737 *M* (ref. 7) and 0.3973 to 2.577 *M* (ref. 12), on NaBr concentration 0.0472 to 0.2439 *M* (ref. 7) and 0.3457 to 3.907 *M* (ref. 13), on NH_4NO_3 concentration 0.0905 to 0.1918 *M* (ref. 7) and 0.2104 to 4.448 *M* (ref. 12), on Na_2SO_4 (ref. 7) and on SrCl_2 (ref. 12). The concentrations recorded in the Tables are correct upto 4 figures.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF ϕ_v OF 2 : 1 ELECTROLYTES WITH DILUTION AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values of ϕ_v		C	Values of ϕ_v	
		Observed	Calculated		Observed	Calculated
Na_2SO_4 Equation (3d) $\phi_v^0=14.4$ K=10.5	0.0072	12.40	12.43	0.0710	14.71	14.75
	0.0480	14.18	14.21	0.0975	15.23	15.23
	0.1658	16.34	16.35	0.4915	19.92	19.92
Na_2SO_4 Equation (3d) $\phi_v^0=8.16$ K=14.9	0.2682	17.76	17.77			
	0.4543	19.59	19.61			
	0.0256	19.34	19.31	0.2334	21.52	21.56
SrCl_2 Equation (3d) $\phi_v^0=17.25$ K=7.0	0.0493	19.84	19.82	0.8137	21.99	21.99
	0.1039	20.50	20.52	0.4026	22.44	22.42
	0.1509	20.94	20.96	0.4691	22.74	22.68
SrCl_2 Equation (3d) $\phi_v^0=14.96$ K=9.98	0.5114	22.95	22.91	0.9292	24.60	24.65
	0.6286	23.43	23.45	1.043	25.00	25.03
	0.7630	23.98	24.03	1.188	25.49	25.48

Discussion

It may be noticed from the data on NaCl, KCl and NaBr recorded in Table 1 that the difference between the values of ϕ_v calculated by using equation (3e) and those observed does not usually exceed 0.02 ml. Only for NaCl at $C=0.0186$ and 0.0612 the difference is 0.06 and 0.04, respectively; but according to the authors' the probable experimental error at these low concentrations is also high. Hence it may be concluded that for the aforesaid electrolytes the agreement between the observed and calculated values is satisfactory over the entire range of concentration recorded.

It may also be noted that when $C=0.1$, 0.06 and 0.04, equation (3e) reduces to equation (3d) for NaBr, NaCl and KCl, respectively as K_1C then becomes equal to 0.02 and hence negligible.

For NH_4NO_3 equation (3d) holds good throughout the concentration range recorded, but the values

of the constants ϕ_v^0 and K are 46.98 and 1.54, respectively in the concentration range $C=0.0905$ to $C=1.627$, and 46.38 and 2.05, respectively in the range $C=1.627$ to $C=4.448$. The variation of the constants is to be attributed to decrease in a , the effective ionic diameter, with decrease in hydration of the ions caused by increase in concentration of the electrolyte. The NO_3^- ion is known to be a strong structure breaker.

The data in Table 2 show that equation (3d) holds good for Na_2SO_4 and SrCl_2 but the constants ϕ_v^0 and K have different values in the different ranges of concentration. The variation of the constants is to be attributed, as in the case of NH_4NO_3 , to decrease in hydration and hence to decrease in a , with the increasing concentration of the electrolytes.

Attention may also be drawn to the fact that the observed values of ϕ_v are expressed in terms of equivalent concentration of the electrolytes in the original paper while those recorded in Table 2 are in terms of molar concentration; hence the difference between the observed and calculated values to be allowed for should be 2(0.02). The percentage difference between the observed and calculated values of ϕ_v , however, remains unaffected.

It may be mentioned that the value of \sqrt{a} found from conductivity data is 2.35 for KCl. Therefore, according to equation (3d) the value of S for KCl is 3.3 since $K=1.72$ and if equation (4) is valid for KCl, than $S_{(v)}=4.4$ at 25°.

A critical consideration of the data recorded in Tables 1 and 2, therefore, leads to the conclusion that the apparent molal volume ϕ_v of the aforesaid electrolytes in solution varies with dilution according to cube root of concentration.

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